

Crop and resource management

Soils

Puddling depth and soil texture influence percolation rate (PR)

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Previous research has emphasized intensity of puddling to minimize percolation losses. Hydraulic conductivity of the puddled layer and the hydraulic head gradient across it theoretically control PR. Thickness of the clay layer on the soil surface is likely to influence hydraulic head gradient. Differences in thickness are due to differential settling of soil particles after puddling, which depends on soil clay content and puddling depth.

We conducted two experiments to study the effect of puddling depth and soil texture on PR. In the first experiment, three soils from Punjab were used. Soils were silt loam (53% sand, 29% silt, and 10% clay), sandy loam

Percolation rate (cm/h)

1. Relationship between percolation rate and thickness of clay layer at the surface for silt loam soil.

Relative percolation rate

(71% sand, 11% silt, and 10% clay), and loamy sand (86% sand, 6% silt, and 8% clay) with bulk density of 1.45, 1.50, and 1.60 Mg/m³, respectively. Soil columns (95 cm long × 10 cm inside diam) were saturated with water and PR was measured in two replications. Water influx was kept at a constant head of 2 cm. Clay particles from a slug put on the top of the soil column settled into layers 0, 0.43, 0.86, 1.72, 2.50, and 3.44 cm thick. Bulk density of the layer was 0.74 Mg/m³.

In the second experiment, puddling depth for each soil was calculated using volume-mass relations and clay content to bring into suspension the same amount of clay as that on top of the columns in the first experiment. Relationships between relative PR and puddling depth were developed for the soils.

2. Relationship between relative percolation rate (RPR) and puddling depth (PD).

PR without a clay layer was 4 mm/h for silt loam, 44 mm/h for sandy loam, and 83 mm/h for loamy sand. PR decreased linearly with thickness of clay layer irrespective of soil texture, which was also true when soil was puddled to bring a specific amount of clay into suspension. (See Figure 1 for the relationship for silt loam.)

The exponential function explained RPR (PR/PR maximum) and puddling depth relationship in the three soils (Fig. 2). The regression coefficient increased with coarseness of soil texture. The intercept value of 1 satisfies upper and lower limits of the function, meaning that when puddling depth is zero, PR equals maximum PR, and when puddling depth is infinite, PR is zero.

These results suggest that to reduce PR to a specific limit, greater puddling depth is needed in coarser soils than in medium-textured soils. Puddling depth rather than intensity appears to help improve control of percolation losses with minimum deterioration of soil structure. ■

Physiology and plant nutrition

Characteristics of rice root growth under salt stress

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We conducted a sand culture pot experiment to investigate the characteristics of rice root growth under salt stress. Seedlings of tolerant CSR-1 and sensitive M1-48 were grown at salinity levels of EC 2.5, 5.4, and 12.7 dS/m, created by adding NaCl, CaCl₂,

and Na₂SO₄ in a 7:2:1 ratio to Hoagland's solution. Four replicates were made.

CSR-1 had greater root volume than M1-48 at both tillering and flowering stages (see table). Roots of CSR-1 were concentrated in the 15-30 cm layer; those of M1-48 were mainly in the 0-15 cm layer. Salinity did not affect root distribution pattern. As salinity increased, root volume and maximum root length were significantly reduced in M1-48 but not in CSR-1, and root dry matter increased marginally in CSR-1.